

Mathematics education, researchers and local communities: A critical encounter in times of pandemic, pareidolia and post-factualism

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Pandemic have increased the importance of social phenomenon involving mathematics and making crisis even more critical. This text studies the current global situation in order to enquire the role of mathematics education researchers in times of crises. A review of research partnerships with communities facing long-term critical situations is done, in order to reflect on the possibilities that mathematics education researchers have nowadays. Theoretical notions from theater anthropology and decolonial studies are borrowed to trigger insights on mathematics education as a field of practice and research.

*If we keep quiet they kill us, and if we talk they do so anyways. So, we talk.
Cristina Bautista Taquinás, Indigenous Nasa leader, killed in 2019*

In this plenary I want to invite the MES-community to revisit a recurring old theme: The relationship between communities and researchers in mathematics education research driven by social, cultural, and/or political interests. Researchers refer to diverse communities: local communities, cultural groups, teachers, or even students. In almost all previous conferences we can find a plenary talk in which this relationship is explicitly addressed or at least implied. The study of this relationship has almost become a genre within our community, in which issues such as the role of the researcher, coherence among methods, principles and ends, impact, validation, agency and reflexivity, just to mention a few, are deployed.

Knowing that the debates about these issues are far from being closed, I want to address some of them with two particularities that can bring new insights and concerns: 1) the contemporary situation assembled in 2020, and 2) features of certain experiences of long-term work with communities. These two particularities will allow me to unfold ways in which mathematics education and political endeavors can nurture each other. My strategy consists of sharing a series of images from research experiences that I am familiar with, in order to formulate questions that mobilize discussion.

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The haze dazes the gaze

Opening MES 8 in Portland, Ubiratan D’Ambrosio foresaw a new era for MES issues. He was almost prophetic: “*there may be no future. Our existence, as a species, is threatened. Our objectives must be even more than social justice and dignity for the human species, must be the survival of our species that is threatened by a societal breakdown*” (D’Ambrosio, 2015, p. 20, original emphasis).

Just six years after we are watching cruel examples of what Ubiratan called social and environmental degradation. MES 9 and MES 10 served to highlight the new threats of post-factualism and the naturalization of crisis. We were experiencing similar or analogous cases of proliferation of (mis)information at different times of the year and (economical) crisis emerged at national scale, as if a ghost visited countries one at a time. First Greece, then Portugal, and so on. Nowadays, with the COVID-19 pandemic those threats get amplified. Crisis gained a global scale and citizens worldwide face the same problems almost simultaneously. Now it is undeniable that we all are on the same boat (although not in the same seat) and more people are conscious of the interconnectedness of our decisions.

Inside this evolving critical situation, mathematics has also amplified its power and agency within the assemblage of things. Mathematics-heavy entities appear everywhere: Models for virus propagation, estimation of vaccines impact, geo-refencing of hot spots of contagious. The incidence of past, current and future public policies at national and global scale, discussions of what metrics to use to assess and compare mortality, lethality, testing, treatments, vaccines and vaccinations. Rates, probabilities, charts, epidemic curves, cost-effectiveness analysis, forecast, simulation models and many more mathematical objects have invaded the public sphere. Debates on objectivity, bias and political consequences of mathematical models exploded everywhere, connecting politicians, scientists, philosophers, groups of interests and layman citizens. All of those debates require having some proficiency in mathematics and, simultaneously, put in doubt the affordances and assumptions that any mathematical model of a pandemic conveys.

I could not imagine a more powerful example of Ole Skovsmose’s ideas on the critical nature of mathematics in society than the COVID-19 situation. Risk, uncertainty, responsibility, mathemacy and several types of mathematical practices in a globalized world are vividly exposed. Knowledge and truth have gone beyond modernist conceptions (Skovsmose, 2009, 2011, 2021). All in one single explosive situation. Decision making processes need to be accomplished in real time at every level (national, regional, municipal, and even personal) with the public scrutiny and turning accountability as a major issue for decision makers. Citizens can be (in/ex)cluded, engaged or discouraged to intervene according to their capacity to understand the mathematical discourse unfolded.

Past and present mathematics education practices exhibit their power within the COVID-19 showcase. Charts with several indicators are used and misused to sustain and criticize public policies. Laypeople assess and question the validity of nation-State measurements of the situation. Personal experiences with the virus, the treatment and the vaccine are used to

mistrust the statistical populational tendencies pointed by experts. Possibility gets equated with certainty (probability equal to 1). Sample results get immediately extrapolated for the whole population. Stochastic thinking is needed not only for citizenship, but for survival, and its absence is evident. Public health offices try to create awareness campaigns and fail miserably. Some people cannot understand the information provided in real-time. Others do not want to understand. Improvements in the propagation models due to new information and subsequent changes in the official policies are labelled as symptoms of improvisation. Hard times to explain rules of scientific method and Popperian falsifiability. Official and dubious information about lethality, infectivity and treatments exploded social networks several times. Conspiracy theories flourish and spread faster than the virus itself, and therefore there emerges the clamor to increase the mathematical-scientific literacy needed to act as a barrier against this tsunami of (mis)information.

Uncertainty in the facts lead to uncertainty in the interpretation of the facts. This is connatural to any state of crisis, and it creates a certain entropy to make the crisis even more critical. However, it is important to inquire the mechanisms that allow the constitution of this situation. Why are fake news so easily propagated? How post-factualism can lead the scene? This is not only because the technological possibilities of sharing information worldwide in real time. It is also because a very old impulse got unleashed: *Pareidolia*, that is the tendency to perceive a specific, often meaningful image, in a random or ambiguous visual pattern. Pareidolia is the basis for psychological exams such as the Rorschach inkblot test, which tries to infer a person's mental state by studying the thoughts or feelings that the person projects into some images (Wikipedia, n.d.).

Pareidolia is one type of *apophenia*, defined as a "tendency to perceive a connection or meaningful pattern between unrelated or random things (such as objects or ideas)." (Merriam-Webster.com, n.d.) There are other kinds of apophenia such as the Gambler's fallacy and the confirmation bias. They are related to situations like echo chambers, or cognitive bias such as the Dunning-Kruger effect. Although these tendencies have been deployed historically to segregate people by political or religious reasons, the internet and the fostering of digital social networks in the last decades have been functional to their unlimited growth and use in generating other type of divisions. One of the results of this dynamic is the political radicalization and polarization that escalate differences, justify violence and damage the social fabric that sustains a community. These worrying *apophanies*¹ seem to be omnipresent since the pandemic exploded and echo chambers seem to be shaping communication more than ever: virus deniers combined with anti-vaccine movements are radicalized by politicians attempting to promote biological passports.

I want to mention just two factors (among many) sustaining the proliferation of echo chambers and mistrust: the historic role of governments and the ways in which information widespreads. The first one is about the eroded confidence of many citizens in private and public institutions. At least in poor countries like mine, the government is historically

¹ An apophany refers to an instance of apophenia that produces the exact opposite of an epiphany.

characterized by the systemic and permanent denial of the most basic human rights of the population; and by the rampant corruption in the state institutions that deviates money from taxes to politicians and the private sector. How can a state like Colombia, that has kidnapped and killed more than 6400 civilians to present them as guerrilla soldiers, ask for credibility? How can the Peruvian government request confidence in medical procedures, after the forced sterilizations of more than 2000 indigenous women? When the official version of facts and events is in the hands of mythomaniacs, citizens are eager to look at other sources.

A second factor is the way in which information is being accessed and filtered. For instance, how search-engines operate in the Internet. It is well known that content creators obtain their profits by the amount of clicks, likes and visits. Algorithms create lists based on the features of the content, registered in meta-data and tags. In order to appear in the top ranks of a list, creators need to make-up their content to look more urgent, paradoxical and scandalous; so they are urged to produce and label content that appeals to the morbid curiosity of the audience, that is, to create clickbait. As a reaction, some educational youtubers have buckled under the pressure and decided to quit their channels because of the induced trivialization of their content. This means that the quality and diversity of contents are constrained and biased towards particular types of information.

Just to summarize this overview, I characterize the contemporary conjuncture as the mingle of new challenges emerging (the current pandemic), not so recent situations (post-factualism), and very old situations (pareidolia); all of these repowered. This explosive cocktail is clearly critical, as it is uncertain, risky and demands responsibility (Skovsmose, 2011). The COVID-19 cocktail operates as anabolic steroids for ongoing social, economic and ecological processes of oppression: Economic exploitation and massive unemployment, surveillance projects of fascist nature, social inequality, ecological deprivation, defunding of public schooling, and many others. All these threats to basic dignity got boosted in the last two years.

Turning on the fog lights

Nonetheless, the pandemic, postfactual and pareidolic (3P) situation also creates possibilities. For instance, Colombian public universities used the pandemics to negotiate with the national government until reaching agreements on full tuition waving for students due to the pandemic, and to enhance part of the digital infrastructure. Of course they did not obtain all resources that public universities deserve, and the conditions are still far from reaching a minimal decency. But certainly students forced the government to do things that were systematically denied for three decades of neoliberal policies of dismantling public education.

Indigenous Nasa people started a self-imposed lockdown in their territory, and gathered healers from different shelters to carry research on the COVID-19 virus. The team of healers experimented with several combination of plants and, after a couple of months, released to the whole community two different recipes: one for prevention and other for treating the symptoms. More recently, when the national government created official vaccination campaigns, Indigenous communities were fearing that the government would provide them

with low quality vaccines or even introduce other diseases among indigenous communities. As a result, indigenous organizations decided not to participate, arguing against the lack of clarity on the procedures, expressing concerns on vaccine effectivity, and defending their indigenous protocols of biosecurity.

During the extended lockdown, the Colombian government also tried to pass a regressive tax law, that would increase the taxation burden on the poorest. That provoked a national strike. In April 28th 2021, there started a social revolt unseen in 50 years. Anger and indignation expressed in unexpected ways. Statues of colonizers were pulled down, public places were renamed, young people made blockages and barricades in strategic points of several main cities. They get organized through social networks and broadcasted live the confrontation with police squads, revealing police brutality.² That was useful to contest the fake news that proliferated through established mainstream media. Television news showed only the riots and looting, prompting the narrative that cities needed to declare martial law to control the protesters.

Internet activism served to make visible other dimensions of the protest. People organized in the neighborhoods and created several lines of resistance. While some conformed the front line of the confrontation, a side line of mothers went to the streets to take care of their kids in the frontline; lines of musicians went to play and serve as incidental soundtrack of the riot! Collectives of lawyers worked, free of charge!, to represent people detained and guarantee their civil rights. Even an anonymous guy who dressed with the Colombian flag was named “Captain Colombia”, in a sarcastic real emulation of the fictional U.S.A. hero. People organized a “communitarian pot” to provide food to front-line protesters. This “pot” consists in closing a street and turning it into a kitchen for whoever needs to be fed. Some of these initiatives became regular and generalized, while some other disappeared or became replaced by others side lines.

Outside the streets, “pedagogical” lines of resistance were also created. In Cali, collectives of lecturers at universities joined high school teachers, engineers and other professionals to create “Pre-Icfes pa'l barrio” [Pre high-stake-test training for the “hood”]. This initiative created a set of free online resources and personal tutoring in mathematics, chemistry, physics and biology, aiming to prepare last year high school students to obtain better grades in the national high-stake test. Variations of this type of initiative has emerged in other cities. In all, the initiative gathers 1.700 volunteers, dispersed around the country and even in other countries in the world, and reaches more than 14.000 youngsters, interested in gaining access to university. Probably the initiative will not succeed in improving the test scores. But

² During the period from April 28 until June 26, 2021 Colombian NGO's have reported violence in the hands of public force: 1,617 victims of physical violence, 44 homicides presumably perpetrated by the Public Force, 2005 arbitrary arrests against protesters, 748 violent interventions of peaceful protests, 82 victims of eye aggressions, 228 cases of firing of weapons, 28 victims of sexual violence and 9 victims of gender-based violence (Temblores ONG et al., 2021).

certainly it mobilizes an important amount of people that usually did not play a part in political actions.

Beyond assessing the efficiency, continuity or coherence of these samples of applied pataphysics, it is important to stress their success in activating spaces of encounter among diverse people who were not were engaged before or were disarticulated. Their success is to be found in the care for the social fabric that pareidolia targets to damage.

Love at third sight

When trying to relate mathematics education (ME) with the recent communitarian contestations mentioned before, some experiences came to my mind. Mônica Mesquita developed, together with groups of fishermen of the Costa de Caparica in Portugal, several projects of communitarian education, using critical ethnography and participatory action research. They first devoted their efforts to obtain unpolluted water to a semi-illegal settlement. More recently they have worked to improve sustainable and safe fishing practices. These experiences have created spaces of formal and informal education that empower communities around issues of collaborative governance, participatory ICT, and fishing legislation. A 20-year process of critical encounters with fisherman, academics, and government representatives has impacted positively on the social conflicts of the Caparica region, working for spatial justice through intellectual justice (Franco & Mesquita, 2019; Mesquita, 2014, 2016).

Since 1998, Adailton Alves da Silva, a Brazilian mathematics educator, has been working with A'uwê/Xavante communities. He began as an advisor in educational projects for this Indigenous group. He still collaborates with the production of didactic materials based on rituals and ceremonies, professional development workshops, and the design and advice on the secondary education curriculum for the Xavante people (da Silva, 2006; da Silva et al., 2021).

Since 2004, Gentil Wejxia, an indigenous educator from the Nasa people in Colombia, has led several educational processes in the sacred region of Tierradentro. In 2008 Gentil became the team leader of an indigenous research group on Nasa mathematics, which studied past and current vernacular practices, relating them with the six universal proto-mathematical activities enunciated by Alan Bishop (Caicedo et al., 2009). Nowadays he is part of the educational experience of *Kiwe Uma*, one of the many enactments of “educación propia” or own indigenous education (Parra & Valero, 2021). This initiative is carried out by a small but growing group of indigenous families that want to develop a culture-rooted education, nurturing their seed (the children) in order to safeguard the indigenous territory, land and worldview. They have structured several development stages for the kids, according to Nasa cultural values and practices. The equivalent to the content in a curriculum is strictly related with the set of skills and knowledge that an indigenous person needs to manage as adult in indigenous and non-indigenous contexts. Gentil has developed further his insights on the cultural dimensions of mathematics. The mathematical component of *Kiwe Uma* includes

both the spirituality behind weaving of some traditional handbags, hats and clothes, as well as the study of statistics and algebra, in order to understand the process of economic and ecologic deprivation that Nasa people have been suffering. This confirms that the *Kiwe Uma* collective decided to teach mathematics for life, but an indigenous life of cultural and political resistance. Kids were deliberately not registered to participate in the national educational system and thus, they would not sit the mandatory high-stake test.

I also acknowledge that MES conferences have been a rich space to meet inspiring experiences. I remember Munir Fasheh telling his story of healing from modern superstitions and the explorations on Mujaawarah in Palestine (Fasheh, 2015) ; the group on Crisis in MES shared Brazilian, Colombian, Indian and Palestinian strategies to deal with educational crises (Marcone et al., 2019; Parra et al., 2017). Gelsa Knijnik has also reported on the educational projects of the land-less movement (MST) in Brazil (Knijnik, 2004, 2006).

It is important to propose a thread that can bond all these experiences, and that sheds light on some of the ways that research and practice on social, cultural and political dimensions of mathematics education has been conducted. To do so, I want to introduce an insight coming from theatre theory, that can be used in many fields of human sciences, and that I find useful for mathematics education in particular. Eugenio Barba is the director of Odin Theatre, a group located in Holstebro, Denmark. He and his group are worldwide recognized for formulating the idea of theater anthropology. When reflecting about the several ways in which performative arts are developed around the world, Barba identifies a special kind of theatre, a “third theatre”, that is:

Almost unknown, it is rarely subject to reflection, it is not presented at festivals and critics do not write about it.

It seems to constitute the anonymous extreme of the theatres recognised by the world of culture: on the one hand, the institutionalised theatre, protected and subsidised because of the cultural values that it seems to transmit, appearing as a living image of a creative confrontation with the texts of the past and the present, or even as a “noble” version of the entertainment business; on the other hand, the avant-garde theatre, experimenting, researching, arduous or iconoclastic, a theatre of changes, in search of a new originality, defended in the name of the necessity to transcend tradition, and open to novelty in the artistic field and within society. (Barba, 1986, p. 193)

From now on, I invite you to play a game of analogies. A “first ME” would be devoted to the ideology of improvement, trying to find and disseminate the “best practices” for mathematics classrooms, in line with official curricula. Large scale projects get funded. A “second ME” would be concerned with studying the complexities of the field, trying to comprehend the dynamics of classroom practices and public policies. Small scale projects receive some funds. Getting back to Barba:

The Third Theatre lives on the fringe, often outside or on the outskirts of the centres and capitals of culture. It is a theatre created by people who define themselves as actors, directors, theatre workers, although they have seldom undergone a traditional theatrical education and therefore are not recognised as professionals.

But they are not amateurs. Their entire day is filled with theatrical experience, sometimes by what they call training, or by the preparation of performances for which they must fight to find spectators. According to traditional theatre standards, the phenomenon might seem insignificant. But from a different point of view, the Third Theatre provides food for thought. (Barba, 1986, p. 193)

Could we think of a “third ME” as one that lives on the margins, one that has to face armed conflict, poverty, famines, cultural extermination, illegal migration? How does a ME that does not locate its strength in institutionalized funding or prestige look like? Although the ordinal third could refer to the “third world”, I think that this kind of mathematics education is being conducted everywhere by teachers, scholars, activists or even enthusiasts, who do not wait for approval or acknowledgement coming from funding agencies or fine academic circles to research and intervene reality. A “third ME” would conceive itself not as the education *for* mathematics, but an education *through* mathematics, just as Ubiratan D’Ambrosio proposed many times.

The third space of ME is what bonds Mônica, Gentil, Adailton, Munir and Gelsa. The third space is inhabited by them and many other people and doings that often are not considered as legitimate ME. They have in common an inner force to experience ME “as a bridge, constantly threatened, between the affirmation of their personal needs, and the necessity of extending them into the surrounding reality” (Barba, 1986, p. 194). A third ME encompasses the diversity of possibilities of adopting a conception of mathematics education research living at the margins. Many of their experiences are developed outside the school, but within politically organized groups; and others happen within the school system.

Third thoughts

In this section I engage in some further considerations (as remarks or extended aphorisms) that will elucidate the affordances of noticing this third region of ME. Some of them paraphrase what Eugenio Barba has proposed about the third theater in (Barba, 1992, 2002). I begin observing that the nomination of “third ME” could be new, but the concerns and purposes subsumed in the nomination are certainly not new. So, it is not aiming to propose a new pedagogic style, neither a new turn. Rather, it performs a sociology of the absences that “amplifies the present by adding to the existing reality what was subtracted from it” (de Sousa Santos, 2012, p. 56): A decolonial move to make visible knowledge, people and stories that were assumed as non-existent.

A third space of ME is not an educational style, nor an alliance of research groups, still less a movement or international association; nor is it a school, a paradigm, or set of techniques or methods. Instead, it points to a way of giving meaning to mathematics education. So, whereas many people wonder if school (and ME) make any sense nowadays (as if it were a thing capable to have or lack anything), a third space assumes that such problem belongs to the people who inhabits school (and ME). It prefers to deal with the question: “Are we able to give meaning to what we do?” This is far from a solipsistic, isolated approach to the problem. It is an awareness that answers need to be singular and embodied in actions.

A search for meaning signifies above all a singular discovery of a craft. It invites to a “patient building up of our own physical, mental, intellectual, and emotional relationship with [teachers, students and knowledge], without conforming to those balanced and proved relationships current at the centre of [mathematics education]” (Barba, 1992, p. 9, paraphrases in brackets). A craft does not fall entirely in techniques or routines, and what is crucial in a craft is the *ethos* that sustain it. An *ethos* is the ensemble of social, linguistic, political, existential, communitarian and ethical behavior, that expresses the ways in which we want to relate our local history with History. Our field is used to be thought in two dimensions, as if what mattered was only policies, ideological tendencies, institutions, learning outcomes, or different methodologies (Barba, 2002). Such framing falls short when inquiring for *ethos* and its concomitant craft. When mathematics education is addressed as solitude, craft, and revolt. Just like Paulus Gerdes did his work until his last day of life. I wonder if this paragraph meets with what Sonia Clareto and Roger Miarka have delineated as “minor mathematics education” (Clareto & Miarka, 2015).

The quest(ion) for a craft opens up an entire new terrain. Who does research? As far as everyone is in the race to create meaning for their own practice, the conventional colonial frontier among the one who thinks and the ones that are thought, gets blurred. It happens a displacement in the *locus of enunciation*³. Such displacement puts in doubt the very concept of research, and also its impact, pertinence and validation. For instance, in the indigenous regions of Cauca, Colombia, educational projects must be formulated and justified in regards of local community agendas of political and cultural resistance. They must involve members as active researchers (and not merely informants). This is to say, the academic outcomes are not the leading force, even as the research goals grow from the inside of community and reach the outside of legislative funding agencies. Mônica Mesquita has had similar experiences in Costa de Caparica. She has shared with me the need to have in mind the “hidden agenda”, setting collectively, first, what would be the gain for the fishing community and, then, making adjustments to present projects to academic instances. The term “hidden” here point to the hybridity in the task. While the agenda is explicit, open, and co-constructed with the community, it is hidden because the bureaucratic eye of institutions is incapable to see it and grasp the vibrant desires for dignity of those involved. This creative role stresses the capacities of communities to generate knowledge for survival, enlarging the horizon of possibilities beyond what heterodox and disciplinary practices can do. These possibilities are part of a sociology of emergences (de Sousa Santos, 2012).

Once the geopolitics of knowledge is noticed, attempts to “include” by “giving voice”, or by “acting on behalf of” should be reconsidered in research. The core idea of research as representation of the *other* is alien to a third ME, because una cosa es el indio, y otra cosa es la antropología. Instead, research becomes an experience of encounter among different entities (individual, groups and even non-human agents), that can be performative and transformative only as far as the experience nurtures the craft of parties involved.

³ Mignolo (2000) introduced this concept first, but we take it here as “the geo-political and body-political location of the subject that speaks” (Grosfoguel, 2011, p. 4).

Just like the emulated third theater, a third ME circulates in a diversity of scenarios, audiences, procedures and outcomes. For instance, grandparents and healers have a central role in the *Kiwe Uma* activities. The simplest notion of school as fixed place operating at certain regular hours is completely detonated by the Nasa proposals of “educación propia”. Participants travel across several *resguardos* (a type of indigenous reservation) and gather according to the moon phases and the healer’ spiritual assessment that determines if the group of kids is spiritually clean and strong to embrace the work session. Mathematics educators visiting the third space embrace their accountability to instances far outside of the OECD-PISA domain.

When the first and second ME describe themselves as exploring a field, they really use the term “field” in a metaphorical way, because they are seldom located and immersed in a particular concrete space. Instead, incarnations of third ME explore a real, concrete field, a land in dispute, such as Palestine, the invaded *fazendas* near Porto Alegre, in Brazil, the illegal settlements of Costa de Caparica in Portugal, or the indigenous *resguardos* in Cauca, Colombia. This is not a pure coincidence. Fighting for the land means fighting for the material conditions of existence, a fight for survival with dignity. The complex articulation between materiality, knowledge and culture is expressed by the Colombian leader Francia Márquez:

Territory for the black people is the real possibility of giving birth to freedom, autonomy, self-determination, it is our space for being. That is why we often harangue: territory is life and life is not for sale, it is loved and defended, likewise community wisdom shows us that *territory is life and life is not possible without territory.* (Marquez, 2020, italics added)

Solidarity with social processes and land, lead us to this enigmatic sentence: with mathematics we can inquire on/in time and space, with a mathematics education we can inquire on the rights to have a time and space.

At this point of the text, I aspire that this paragraph would be a truism: a third ME addresses the political nature of mathematics education in a particular way. Whereas conscious of the structural constraints that shapes school, education, mathematics and research, it decides to focus in the here-and-now of its particular political agency. Paraphrasing the anthropologist Joan Rappaport: “while some scholars engage in [political] description with an eye to analyzing it, [third ME researchers] study [politics] to act upon it” (Rappaport, 2008, pp. 20–21, paraphrases in brackets)

A last remark here could be the first to be said. The three types of regions in mathematics education research are not exhaustive nor exclusionary. There could be other unknown types of regions and many shared spaces among regions. It is important to stress that a third space is not conceived as superior or better than the others; it mainly indicates a different arrangement of priorities. Namely, whereas a first type is devoted to understand “how you do mathematics education”, and the second will study “what mathematics education you do”, a third will ask “why you do mathematics education”. It is natural that each one of the three questions conveys part of the others, but depending on which one is prioritized, the other two questions are answered differently.

Close encounters of the third kind

This section explores the question of how we can address research and practices of mathematics education (ME) in the mingle of the 3Ps (pandemic, post-factualism and pareidolia). So far, I have focused on a particular stance about the field, called the third ME, in which collaborative practices of research with communities are central, and a permanent observance on ME research agency leads the practice.

I contend that the current context of threats to human survival and transcendence demands a reframing of the terms and purposes in which mathematics education researchers conceive their practice, especially when they encounter communities. The concept of *craft* can guide such reframing.

An appeal to consider the theoretical and methodological possibilities of including practitioners' agency into academic research projects has been raised by Renuka Vithal in MES 2 and by Orlando Fals-Borda in MES 3 as part of a paradigm shift in the social sciences. They discussed the dichotomy subject/object of study and explored the political relevance of participatory methods, ending with an invitation to seek possibilities to make more horizontal the research relation⁴ (Fals-Borda, 2002; Vithal, 2000).

Almost 20 years later, the framework of decolonial studies (Castro-Gómez & Grosfoguel, 2007; de Sousa Santos, 2010; Smith, 2013; Zavala, 2013) lead us to go further in the paradigm shift. What would happen if not only local practitioners are welcomed on board to design and execute academic research projects on mathematics education, but also scholars try to join communitarian social processes that involve mathematics? What if we turn the inclusive action to ourselves? What if we do not assume to have the power to include, but rather have the aim of being included? What would happen if academic scholars decided not to have the main role in the play? My invitation, then, is to explore again (and still differently) the possibilities to make the research relation more horizontal.

A first thing that could happen is that scholars will need to consider the existence of mathematics education research outside the school, conducted by people interested in learning mathematics in action. Scopus-free researchers, working with PISA-free students! Many of them live on the margins, in the third ME. Some others live in between.

Consciousness on the responsibilities of contesting the matrix of hierarchizations that sustain modern rationality will help ME researchers to establish respectful relationships with communities. Collaborative and participatory approaches could be compatible with his/her decisions, unfolding exercises of co-theorization, mutual interrogation or endogenous research methods that build trust among different stakeholders involved. Instead of reducing accountability to heterodox criteria (such as consistency, scope or validity) or to the problems of reflexivity, academic researchers could also be aware of the problems of *symmetry*. The latter can be thought as "the study of how the participation of both researchers and practitioners has been conceived, unfolded, enacted, registered, and assessed in research"

⁴ Concerns on practices of intellectual extractivism were raised by Setati in MES2.

(Parra, 2018, p. 150). Symmetry is also crossed by the complex power relationships around representativeness, legitimacy and intellectual property that surround any research. Integral part of mathematics education researcher's craft is the management of this complexity.

As Vithal and Fals-Borda noted, collaborative processes are inevitably critical. They demand intense interactions among different expectations, skills and backgrounds. Join communitarian processes attempt to congregate heterogeneous agents. This is precisely the opposite of the dissociative power of pareidolia and echo chambers, which segregate homogenous agents. 3P does not like these kinds of barterers!

In a very paradoxical way, this type of detours and escapes from the normal flux of academic practices could bring us to a renovated mathematics: One like the envisioned by Orlando Fals-Borda and Ubiratan D'Ambrosio; one that studies and expands the ways in which local communities have survived and transcended for many years (some of them for more than 5 centuries!). The third ME came to learn ethnomathematics in action. It is possible to conceive a kind of mathematics that turns its efforts to safeguard life, and that bring answers to the urgent needs of people; a mathematics that can support the struggle of people organized around the defense of a territory, like the experiences in Porto Alegre, Costa de Caparica, Cauca, or any other illegal⁵ settlement.

Decoloniality has stated it clear and loud: An *ecology of knowledge(s)* rejects dichotomic thinking; it understands the relevance of disciplinary knowledge to contribute to the well-being. And for that reason, it does not endorse anti-intellectual gestures, like the monster currently in charge of Brazil, who has taken advantage of the COVID-19 cocktail as a biological weapon for exterminating indigenous people in the Brazilian Amazonia. Indigenous people kick back and share the developments of their struggle to their Brazilian brothers. The scientists of Instituto Butantan in São Paulo are doing the same. Every help counts now to stop the current genocide. A third ME researcher necessarily contests post-factualism.

In the time of the 3Ps, humanity needs to learn how to establish sustainable relations with non-human existences⁶. Capitalists and colonialists never understood how to make it (they only want to see measures, profits and borders in the land). The ones who understood that the Earth is not a resource to exploit but the very condition of our existence have been living and resisting for centuries. These are the communities of indigenous peoples, farmers, fishermen, among others. Decoloniality articulates diverse types of knowledge, through cultural encounters that multiply experiences and share wisdom. A third ME researcher knows the importance of entering and committing to communitarian territories to listen, share, care and learn how to resist.

⁵ Sometimes its illegality means that it is managed collectively and has not been measured (devoured) by capitalism.

⁶ Paola Valero (2019) asked already what would be the mathematics education compatible with the imminent "new climatic regime", because that regime challenge many assumptions that sustain the current mathematics education.

Third time's the charm (or maybe not)

An important contribution that an ethical stance can bring to the field of ME is the chance to elaborate on certain insights that are gaining currency within the MES community. Colleagues (for instance, Andrade-Molina, Baldino, Pais, Valero) have raised warnings on the chances that ME research has to truly impact the school system in contemporary neoliberal societies. They have pointed out several constraints, like the capitalist system that needs to produce surplus-value at any time, or the subjectification processes that occur for students, teachers and researchers. Broadly speaking, colleagues refer to the *mechanisms of capture* (a.k.a Foucaultian dispositif), and point out that there are several mechanisms of capture jeopardizing the possibilities of “changing” the system.

So we are always facing the danger of being deceived, as we think that we are struggling against oppression, when in fact we are being allowed by the dominant class to do so, just to cool down the rebellion. As I said before, the core things, like assessment and school, are here to stay. (Pais, 2008)

In that line of thought, when addressing the role of mathematics (and school) within the new normal state of global crisis due to the 3Ps (pandemia, postfactualism and pareidolia), ME researchers will need to be very careful not to get trapped by the mechanisms of capture, and not to end up subsuming their efforts to make a critical mathematics education instrumental to the increase of human exploitation. I could not agree more; that is definitely a possibility. Furthermore, I am sure that such a thing is happening already. However, if we have the analytical acumen to perceive how transnational forces of political and economic domination enter the school or enact themselves in mathematics education research, then we should also have the insight to notice how local forces of resistance also seek school and university spaces. Because education is just one more set-up in this antagonistic relationship, and since we inhabit that set-up, it is up to us to address the situation.

Previous sections showed us people around the world using the pandemic to create spaces and lines of cultural and political resistance. They appeal to an ethos of resistance, to activate *mechanisms of escape* (a.k.a Foucaultian counter-conduct or Deleuzian lines of escape or flight). My point is that ME researchers can indeed find resources to block the mechanisms of capture by engaging with sectors of society that are activating the mechanisms of escape. Playing with the words of Barba, one could ask:

Why do they choose [mathematics education] in particular as a means of change, when we are well aware that other factors determine the reality in which we live? Is it a question of blindness, of self-delusion?

Perhaps for them, [mathematics education] is a means to find their own way of being present and seeking more human relationships with the purpose of creating a social cell in which intentions, aspirations and personal needs begin to be transformed into actions. (Barba, 1986, p. 194, paraphrases in brackets)

A disenchanted but powerful idea of utopia is suggested here. There is no possible salvation, neither a hedonistic approach is attempted. I do not expect to “solve” the societal problems of post-factualism or pareidolia when I proposed to work more closely with

A. Parra

communities. I intend to do something different, closer to the concept of *hope* from Václav Havel: “It is not the conviction that something will turn out well, but the certainty that something makes sense, regardless of how it turns out” (Havel, 1990, p. 181).

Then, we should not wait for ME to make sense, but we should give it meaning. This in itself is a political act that is neither romantic nor useless. This is precisely the main task: to develop a craft, a care of the self:

The hell of the living is not something that will be. If there is one, it is what is already here, the hell we live in every day, that we make by being together. There are two ways to escape suffering it. The first is easy for many: accept the hell, and become such a part of it that you can no longer see it. The second is risky and demands constant vigilance and apprehension: seek and learn to recognize who and what, in the midst of hell, are not hell, then make them endure, give them space (Calvino, 1978).

It is to develop a revolt, a rebellion, conceived as the stubbornness of doing something that is doomed to fail, of doing what is needed to do, or of doing what we are required to do in order to find/build meaning to our path.

Pataphysics is not romanticism, insofar as it boycotts the status of the thinkable. It is a corrosive force that denaturalizes normality.

*With broken temples and arms beaten,
We sound the fanfare of those never surrendered
and of the always defeated!
(Leon de Greiff, Sarabanda, 1929)*

*O [assessment], where is your victory?
O [mandatory curriculum], where is your sting?
(1 Corinthians, 15: 55-57)*

*I look for life in death,
for health in sickness,
for freedom in prison,
a way out from the impasse,
and loyalty in the Judas.
But my destiny, from which I would
never expect anything good,
has decreed with the Gods
that, since I ask for the impossible,
they won't even give me the possible.
(Miguel de Cervantes Saavedra)*

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A. Parra

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